

Spider diversity of the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Annette vd Berg²

¹DSI/NRF Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda; ² ARC technician (retired)

ABSTRACT: SANSA participates in several national research projects. One such project by the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) took place on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province, where methods to control the Red-billed Quelea (*Quelea quelea*) were examined. The Springbok Flats is an extensive plain of fertile thornveld–grassland situated in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo. Surveys to sample invertebrates were conducted on six farms over 27 months, from January 2001 to March 2003. The spiders sampled were sorted and identified at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection. A total of 245 species and 157 genera from 38 families were recorded. The spiders sampled across the Springbok Flats are part of the SANSA Limpopo survey project and represent 27% of Limpopo spiders and 40% of the Waterberg survey.

Keywords: biodiversity, Savanna Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the Limpopo Province. One such project was undertaken by the Agricultural Research Council on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province as part of research into controlling red-billed Quelea (*Quelea quelea*). In South Africa, the control of the red-billed quelea is formally organised and government-led, with support from research bodies, farmers, and environmental regulators. Quelea control is implemented at the provincial level, especially in high-risk provinces such as Limpopo. The ARC conducts research on Quelea population dynamics, migration and breeding patterns, and alternative and non-chemical control methods (Van der Walt 1999). They identify breeding and roosting sites; carry out ground control, nest destruction, and limited chemical control and liaise directly with farmers and local municipalities.

The red-billed Quelea are small, sparrow-like birds with bright red conical bills (Fig. 2). They are found throughout sub-Saharan Africa, from Senegal and Sudan to South Africa. They prefer open grasslands, savannas, and cultivated areas, often near water sources and avoid dense forests and high-altitude regions. They are highly nomadic, moving thousands of kilometres annually in response to rainfall and food availability. They are extremely gregarious and form massive flocks that move in synchronised patterns, creating spectacular “rolling clouds” in the sky and can number in the millions (Fig. 3). They roost in dense vegetation and breed in huge colonies, sometimes covering entire landscapes. Primarily granivorous, feeding on seeds of wild grasses, but when natural food is scarce, they raid cereal crops such as sorghum, millet, wheat, and rice. During breeding, they supplement their diet with insects (e.g., grasshopper nymphs, termites) for protein (Van der Walt, 1999).

The Springbok Flats is an extensive plain situated in Limpopo, South Africa. To the east, it includes the towns of Roedtan, Tuinplaas, and Settlers. The 80 km-wide and 130 km-long swaths of land are oriented in a northeasterly direction. The plain, which is exceptionally flat and situated at an altitude of 1,000 m above sea level, experiences warm summers (shielded from cold winds by surrounding uplands) and dry winters. An annual rainfall of about 620 mm is the norm. It is considered a highly fertile thornveld–grassland area (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Surveys were undertaken on the Springbok Flats (SF) by members of ARC-Plant Health and Protection, to determine the effect of control methods of the red-billed quelea on invertebrates such as spiders, and the sampled material was sorted and identified at the National Collection of Arachnida (Van den Berg *et al.*, 2002).

Figures 1–3. 1. The thornveld–grassland of the Springbok Flats. 2. Male red-billed quelea. 3. Swarm of birds causing damage to crops. Credits: Agricultural Research Council.

Study area: The surveys took place in the Springbok Flats, an extensive plain of fertile thornveld–grassland situated in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006). Sampling took place on six farms stretching from Settlers, Roedtan to Naboomspruit: Roedtan (-24.60, 29.08); Tuinplaas (-24.89, 28.73); Settlers, Farm Bekendevlei (-24.60, 29.08); Settlers, Lodge (-25.01, 28.88); Settlers, Wildskamp (-24.60, 29.08); Settlers, Farm Tweekansen (-25.49, 28.57) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The area sampled on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province.

Figures 5–7. Springbok Flats sampling 5. The habitat. 6. Beating the trees sampling spiders. 7. Pitfall traps to sample the ground dwellers.

Collecting methods: Spiders were sampled monthly using pitfall traps for ground fauna and beating and sweeping to sample vegetation (Figs 6 & 7).

Collecting period: The survey was conducted over 27 months, from January 2001 to March 2003.

Voucher specimens: All the material was sorted and identified in the National Collection of Arachnida (non-Acari) (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection. All the voucher specimens were deposited in the NCA.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or known only from type locality, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (data deficient).

Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were of least concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC.

Endemicity value: The endemicity values for each species sampled at the SF are provided in Table 3 & 4. Five endemicity categories are recognized:

- 5—species are only known from the type locality (Springbok Flats).
- 4—species known only from the Limpopo Province endemic (LE).
- 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE).
- 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa, endemic (STHE).
- 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region, endemic (AE).
- 0—also known from outside the Afrotropical Region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 6380 spiders represented by 245 species, 157 genera, from 38 families, were recorded from the SF (Tables 1 & 2). The SF survey forms part of the SANSA Limpopo survey project (Table 1). The spiders sampled at SF represent 27% of the 905 species recorded from Limpopo, and 40% of the 600 species recorded in the Waterberg District survey, and 10.8% of the South African species (Table 1).

TABLE 1: Spider diversity sampled from different sites in the Limpopo Province and South Africa.

AREA	FAM	GEN	SPP.	REFERENCE
South Africa	71	495	2265	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2023)
Limpopo	60	346	905	Foord <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Waterberg dist	54	292	600	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (in press)
Springbokflats	38	157	245	present

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SP.)

FAMILIES	G	SP.	%	FAMILIES	G	SP.	%
Agelenidae	2	2	0.8	Oonopidae	2	3	1.2
Araneidae	16	28	11.4	Orsolobidae	1	1	0.4
Barychelidae	2	2	0.8	Oxyopidae	3	10	4.0
Caponiidae	1	1	0.4	Palpimanidae	2	2	0.8
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	0.4	Philodromidae	5	7	2.9
Corinnidae	6	7	2.9	Pholcidae	1	2	0.8
Ctenidae	2	2	0.8	Pisauridae	3	3	1.2
Cyrtacheniidae	2	5	2.0	Prodidomidae	2	4	1.6
Dictynidae	3	3	1.2	Salticidae	16	28	11.4
Eresidae	2	2	0.8	Segestriidae	1	1	0.4
Gnaphosidae	17	42	17.1	Selenopidae	1	1	0.4
Hahniidae	1	1	0.4	Sicariidae	1	1	0.4
Hersiliidae	2	3	1.2	Sparassidae	3	3	1.2
Idiopidae	3	3	1.2	Theraphosidae	3	3	1.2
Linyphiidae	4	4	1.6	Theridiidae	7	10	4.0
Liocranidae	1	1	0.4	Thomisidae	15	24	9.8
Lycosidae	9	12	4.9	Trachelidae	4	4	1.6
Mimetidae	1	1	0.4	Uloboridae	1	1	0.4
Oecobiidae	1	1	0.4	Zodariidae	10	15	6.1
				157 245			

Family diversity: Of the 38 spider families collected from SF (Tables 2 & 4), the four most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (42 spp.), Salticidae and Araneidae, both with 28 spp., followed by the Thomisidae (24 spp.). Eleven families are represented by singletons. All the sampled specimens in the NCA are available for taxonomic research, and two SF species were described as new to science: *Fuchiba aquilonia* Haddad & Lyle, 2008 (Trachelidae) (Fig. 8), and *Zelotes songus* FitzPatrick, 2007 (Gnaphosidae) (Fig. 9)

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Springbok Flats in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo Province.

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	6	2.4
Data deficient DD	4	1.6
Least concern LC	235	95.9
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	21	8.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	109	44.5
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	60	24.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	45	18.4
4 – Limpopo endemics (LE)	5	0.8
5 – Type locality (Springbok Flats)	2	0.4

Conservation status: Six species from six families could not be identified to species level and were not evaluated (NE). (Tables 3 & 4). They belong to genera in the families Araneidae, Ctenidae, Dictynidae, Oonopidae and Oxyopidae that have not yet been revised in South Africa.

Of the four Data Deficient species, *Brachionopus tristis* (Purcell, 1903) (Theraphosidae), *Idiops gunningi* Hewitt, 1913 (Idiopidae) (Fig. 11), *Zelotes songus* (Gnaphosidae) (Fig. 9) and *Prodidomus simoni* Dalmás, 1919 (Prodidomidae) (Fig. 10) are known only from one sex, and they have a restricted distribution, so more information is needed to determine their status. Most species (95.9%) have a wide distribution and are of Least Concern.

Endemism: 21 species of SF (44.5%) have a wide African distribution, and 8.7% are also found in countries outside Africa. Sixty species (24.5%) are found in southern Africa; 55 species (22.5%) are endemic to South Africa; five are Limpopo endemics; and two are known only from the SF.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the staff of the Arachnology Unit of the Biosystematics Programme, ARC—Plant Health and Protection, for their assistance with processing and databasing the collected material and Charles Haddad, Vida vd Walt and the late Peter Webb for sharing their photographs.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LOTZ L.N., BOOYSEN R., STEENKAMP R.C. & FOORD S.H. 2023. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 64(3): 221–289.

MUCINA L. & RUTHERFORD M.C. 2006. The vegetation of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. *Strelitzia* 19. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria.

VAN DEN BERG A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. VAN JAARVELD M.J. & VAN DER WALT E. 2002. Red-billed quelea control on the Springbok Flats: impact on the Arachnida fauna (Araneae). 7th African Arachnological Colloquium.

VAN DER WALT E. 1999. Research at PPRI on Environmental Effects of Quelea Control Operations. Workshop on Research Priorities for Migrant Pests of Agriculture in Southern Africa, Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria, South Africa, 24–26 March 1999.

Figures 8–11. 8. *Fuchiba aquilonia* (C. Haddad). 9. *Zelotes songus* (P. Webb). 10. *Prodidomus simoni* (V. vd Walt). 11. *Idiops gunningi* (Peter Webb).

Figures 12–26. Spiders of the Springbok Flats. 12. *Eriovixia excelsa*. 13. *Dresserus colsoni*. 14. *Haplodrassus stationis*. 15. *Zelotes frenchi*. 16. *Hogna spenceri*. 17. *Oxyopes schenkeli*. 18. *Thanatus dorsilineatus*. 19. *Hyllus brevitarsis*. 20. *Natta horizontalis*. 21. *Thyene inflata*. 22. *Thyene ogdeni*. 23. *Hewittia gracilis*. 24. *Thomisops sulcatus*. 25. *Xysticus fagei*. 26. *Orthobula radiata*. Credits: Peter Webb

TABLE 4: Spiders of the Springbok Flats listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEN), LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated.

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN	SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
1. Family Agelenidae				8. Family Cyrtaucheniidae			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevivalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Benoitia raymondeae</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa nuda</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
2. Family Araneidae				<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa rufescens</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	3	LC	SAE	<i>Homostola zebrina</i> Purcell, 1902	2	LC	STHE
<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE	9. Family Dictynidae			
<i>Araneus</i> sp. (new)		NE		<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C	<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	10. Family Eresidae			
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 13)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Acantharachne seydeli</i> Giltay, 1935	1	LC	AE	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	11. Family Gnaphosidae			
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ammozenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889) (Fig. 12)	0	LC	C	<i>Aneplasa interrogationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C. L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hypsosinga holzaphelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes decoratus</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes flavipes</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus bechuanicus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus helenae</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus lophognathus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus splendens</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus stationis</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig. 14)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	<i>Leptopilos vasivulva</i> Haddad & Booyesen, 2022	2	LC	STHE
<i>Singa albodorsata</i> Kauri, 1950	3	LC	SAE	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Micaria bispicula</i> Booyesen & Haddad, 2021	2	LC	STHE
3. Family Barychelidae				<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pisenor arcturus</i> (Tucker, 1917)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Pterotracha auris</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Sipalolasma humicola</i> (Benoit, 1965)	1	LC	AE	<i>Rastellus kariba</i> Platnick & Griffin, 1990	2	LC	STHE
4. Family Caponiidae				<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C
<i>Caponia chelifera</i> Lessert, 1936	2	LC	STHE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
5. Family Cheiracanthiidae				<i>Trachyzelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Cheiracanthium vansonii</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
6. Family Corinnidae				<i>Xerophaeus lunulifer</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cambalida dippenaarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus patricki</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Coenoptychus mutillicus</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes aridus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 15)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Corinnomma semiglabrum</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginous</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pronophaea proxima</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	<i>Zelotes humilis</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
7. Family Ctenidae				<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Anahita</i> sp.		NE		<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE				

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Zelotes otavi</i> Fitzpatrick, 2007	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
<i>Zelotes songus</i> FitzPatrick, 2007 (Fig. 9)	5	DD	LE
<i>Zelotes tuckeri</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Zelotes zonognathus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
12. Family Hahniidae			
<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
13. Family Hersiliidae			
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE
<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
14. Family Idiopidae			
<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
<i>Idiops gunningi</i> Hewitt, 1913 (Fig. 11)	4	DD	SAE
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
15. Family Linyphiidae			
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
<i>Metaleptyphantus perexiguus</i> (Simon & Ostearius melanopygius (O. P.-Cambridge, 1879)	1	LC	AE
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
16. Family Liocranidae			
<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
17. Family Lycosidae			
<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Hippasosa guttata</i> (Karsch, 1878)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pardosa umtalica</i> Purcell, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Wadicosa oncka</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
18. Family Macrobnidae			
<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
19. Family Mimetidae			
<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
20. Family Oecobiidae			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
21. Family Oonopidae			
<i>Gamasomorpha australis</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
<i>Orchestina</i> sp.		NE	
22. Family Orsolobidae			
<i>Azania lobus lawrencei</i> Griswold & Platnick, 1987	2	LC	STHE
23. Family Oxyopidae			
<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1927 (Fig. 17)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3		NE	
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
24. Family Palpimanidae			
<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
25. Family Philodromidae			
<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
26. Family Pholcidae			
<i>Smeringopus atomarius</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
27. Family Pisauridae			
<i>Euprostenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Perenethis simoni</i> (Lessert, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
28. Family Prodidomidae			
<i>Prodidomus simoni</i> Dalmas, 1919 (Fig. 10)	6	DD	SFE
<i>Theuma ababensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Theuma fusca</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Theuma purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
29. Family Salticidae			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyryba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha alba</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Helaffricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hispo georgius</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1892)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus argyrotaxus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus brevitaris</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 19)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Mogrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879 (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesolowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesolowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
<i>Phlegra simplex</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesotowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stenaelurillus termitophagus</i> (Wesotowska & Cumming, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873) (Fig. 21)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus lesserti</i> (Wesotowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
30. Family Segestriidae			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
31. Family Selenopidae			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
32. Family Sicariidae			
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
33. Family Sparassidae			
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Olios sjostedti</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE
34. Family Theraphosidae			
<i>Brachionopus tristis</i> Purcell, 1903	4	DD	SAE
<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE
<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
35. Family Theridiidae			
<i>Emertonella episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda triangulosa</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	3	LC	AE
<i>Theridion pictum</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
36. Family Thomisidae			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928 (Fig. 23)	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1846)	0	LC	C
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Ozyptila caenosa</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
<i>Parasmodix quadrituberculata</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stiphropus bisigillatus</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema vallononi</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
37. Family Trachelidae			
<i>Afrocecto plana</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	1	LC	AE
<i>Fuchiba aquilonia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008 (Fig. 26)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897 (Fig. 26)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trachelas pusillus</i> Lessert, 1923	1	LC	AE
38. Family Uloboridae			
<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
39. Family Zodariidae			
<i>Caesetius inflatus</i> Jocqué, 1991	1	LC	AE
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Capheris subtilis</i> Jocqué, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	1	LC	AE
<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	1	LC	AE
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores annetteae</i> Jocqué, 1990	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores magicus</i> Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores triarmatus</i> Lessert, 1929	1	LC	AE
<i>Heradida bicincta</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Microdiores</i> sp.		NE	
<i>Palfuria spirembolus</i> Szűts & Jocqué, 2001	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ranops robinae</i> Jocqué & Henrard, 2020	3	LC	SAE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE